

Exploring Primary School Teachers' Perspectives in Integrating AI into STEM Education through Modular STEM Activities

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Abstract: *This study explores the integration of AI education into a Hong Kong primary school through modular STEM activities, addressing challenges related to teacher preparedness and curriculum design. Collaborating with three STEM teachers, we co-developed hands-on learning modules delivered via an after-school club. Qualitative analysis of observations, interviews, and learning artifacts revealed teachers' initial conceptual and technical struggles, which were mitigated by iterative co-design and low-code tools. While modular resources lowered entry barriers, dependency risks emerged, particularly among novice educators relying on predefined learning content. Experienced teachers demonstrated adaptive innovation, repurposing STEM pedagogies for AI contexts. Findings emphasize the dual role of modular STEM activities—standardizing implementation while enabling flexibility for skilled educators. Furthermore, the findings underscore the need for structured teacher professional development (TPD) that provides scaffolded support to promote autonomy among in-service teachers, fostering critical AI literacy and pedagogical agency.*

Keywords: AI education, STEM activities, teacher professional development, co-design, modular learning

1. Introduction

Educational stakeholders are collaborating to incorporate AI education into K–12 curricula, preparing the next generation for a future shaped by rapidly advancing AI, with early exposure helping to establish a solid foundation for future learning (Walter, 2024). Following Hong Kong's prior experience in developing an AI curriculum for secondary schools (Chiu et al., 2022), this study serves as a pilot project focusing on age-appropriate AI education at the primary school level to lay the groundwork for earlier and more comprehensive AI literacy. Dai et al. (2023) demonstrated that primary school teachers can create an inclusive and accessible AI curriculum by embedding it within an existing STEM framework while ensuring academic rigor. Therefore, we argue that active STEM exploration in Hong Kong primary schools (Wong, 2017) provides a viable pathway for incorporating AI into the curriculum. For instance, despite the complexity of AI, independent learning modules covering AI concepts, applications, and ethics can be developed to allow for flexible implementation and easy entry for beginners (Kandlhofer et al., 2023). However, integrating AI into educational settings presents challenges, particularly due to teachers' limited preparedness in this emerging arena. Ng et al. (2022) argue that the rapid development of AI-based tools by technology companies—often without sufficient consideration of teachers' and students' needs—may further overwhelm educators. To bridge this burgeoning gap, we engaged in iterative co-design with three Hong Kong primary STEM teachers, implementing a series of modular STEM activities while tracking teachers' perspectives in integrating AI into STEM education throughout the process.

2. Methods

2.1. Context and Participants

This study was conducted in a private co-educational primary school in Hong Kong—well-equipped with STEM learning resources—focusing on three teachers (see Table 1 for background information) who collaborated with our research team to design and implement a series of modular STEM activities centered on AI technologies. These activities were delivered through an after-school STEM club, comprising 17 mixed-age students from Primary 4 to Primary 6. The students were selected for their strong interest and aptitude in STEM, as they frequently engaged in innovative projects for STEM competitions under their teachers' guidance.

2.2. Collaboration between the research team and the teachers

To initiate the collaboration, the research team designed a preliminary framework for modular STEM activities, integrating key aspects of STEM education, such as interdisciplinarity, constructionist learning, and real-world problem-solving (Ali, 2021; Ali et al., 2024). This framework was developed as a robust instructional package, including teacher guidelines, student workbooks, and activity slides. To ensure effective co-design, we first supported teachers in gaining a broad overview of AI by providing appropriate resources and helping them create tailored learning content. Training sessions were then conducted to guide them through each learning module while offering relevant background information. Once they became familiar with the content, they assessed whether the planned activities aligned with students' cognitive levels, refining or devising new activities as needed. Their feedback informed formative adjustments to the learning modules, ensuring their relevance and effectiveness. As the implementation progressed, the teachers engaged in regular discussions with us, reviewing and refining the content before each session. This iterative process of training, feedback, and continuous refinement aimed to facilitate the seamless integration of AI education into the classroom.

Table 1. Background information of three teachers

Name (Pseudonym)	Scott	Winnie	Yvette
Gender	M	F	F
Age Range	40 - 45	25 - 30	20 - 25
Teaching Subjects	Science Studies, General Studies	Math, Science Studies, Computer Studies	Math, Computer Studies
Years of School	17	5	2
Subject-teaching			

2.3. Final Learning Modules

Through the aforementioned collaboration, the final series of activities was implemented as five learning modules across eight once-weekly sessions, each lasting approximately 50 minutes. These modules included: (1) “*What is AI?*”, introducing AI through discussions and interactions with a virtual assistant (e.g., Siri); (2) “*What is Machine Learning?*”, using Google's Quick, Draw! to demonstrate supervised learning through pattern recognition; (3) “*Utilizing Machine Learning in Daily Problem-Solving*”, leveraging Google Teachable Machine (GTM) to train an image recognition model applied to a Micro-Bit for a smart waste bin prototype; (4) “*How Classifiers Work: Supervised and Unsupervised Learning*”, contrasting supervised and unsupervised methods through card-sorting activities; and (5) “*Exploring GenAI and Its Risks*”, analyzing ethical concerns by comparing human- and AI-generated content (e.g., Midjourney, Sora). Each module prioritized hands-on engagement to connect AI concepts to real-world contexts.

2.4. Data Source and Analysis

We conducted an exploratory study to gain insights into the perspectives of participating teachers in integrating AI into their classrooms through modular STEM activities. Multiple qualitative data sources, collected across all stages of the collaboration, were used for triangulation and to create a comprehensive description. These included: (a) participant

observations (e.g., field notes, video recordings) from AI workshops, project meetings, and activity implementations; (b) teaching artifacts (e.g., revised activity slides and student workbooks); and (c) post-implementation interviews, during which each of the three teachers was individually interviewed for 45–60 minutes using semi-structured interview questions. To analyze this extensive data, an interpretive approach was employed (Merriam, 1998). Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2012), noted for its flexibility, was used to identify key meaning patterns and capture the major perspectives teachers demonstrated as the collaboration progressed. Narrative analysis (Fina et al., 2021) complemented this by preserving continuity and contradictions in teachers' experiences, offering a holistic understanding of their thematic interpretations.

3. Findings

This section presents selected findings on the participating teachers' perspectives. The thematic analysis identified *three* overarching themes that aligned with their predominant narratives, later confirmed through narrative analysis.

3.1. Challenges in Teachers' Conceptual Understanding and Technical Adaptability

The implementation of AI education revealed interconnected challenges in the teachers' conceptual understanding and technical adaptability. Initially, knowledge-related anxiety stemmed from AI's disciplinary complexity, with experienced educators like Scott expressing concern: “*As I can't fully grasp the concept of AI, I worry about providing students with an incorrect entry point...*” (Preparatory Meeting). He also noted that the school's prior attempts to introduce AI instruction had been hampered by teaching materials that prioritized tool-specific procedures over conceptual explanations, forcing teachers to rely on step-by-step tutorials without fostering deeper understanding.

Targeted training sessions addressed these gaps, prompting critical reflection—for instance, Scott recognized that traffic light tasks, with their fixed outcomes, poorly modelled machine learning's predictive logic (Training Session). Classroom practice itself became a catalyst for growth: Winnie, a less experienced teacher, noted how teaching AI deepened her grasp of concepts like supervised learning, while novice educator Yvette acknowledged that “*reviewing the material myself [while teaching] deepened my understanding*” (Interview). Yet systemic constraints persisted. The teachers' expertise remained bound to module content, with Winnie admitting her understanding was “*limited to the slides I teach*” due to the absence of formal AI integration (Interview). This dependency hindered instructional autonomy, as Scott conceded: “*We rely heavily on your [researchers'] guidance... It's your ideas we implement*” (Interview).

These conceptual uncertainties amplified technical struggles during the implementation. The teachers reported that programming complexity—evident in prior STEM lessons derailed by Python coding errors (Winnie, Preparatory Meeting)—prompted choices of low-code tools like GTM and Micro-Bit. While these tools enabled tangible projects (e.g., AI-powered smart trash bins) and reduced syntax barriers, they risked oversimplification. Scott critiqued GTM's narrow utility, stating, “*The model can't distinguish glass from plastics, limiting real-world problem-solving*” (Progress Meeting), while interdisciplinary knowledge gaps hindered deeper task elaboration. Attempts to leverage GenAI (e.g., GPT-4o) for code generation failed due to prompt specificity demands, revealing persistent reliance on external expertise.

3.2. Teachers' Adaptation of AI Instruction Through Existing Pedagogical Expertise

Leveraging their experience in project-based and inquiry-based STEM teaching, the teachers intuitively adopted constructionist approaches to co-design the learning modules, despite their limited AI expertise. They applied these approaches in AI contexts, for example, by integrating interactions with Siri—a virtual assistant that students were familiar with—to highlight AI's prevalence and key features, such as natural interaction, through firsthand experience. Most notably, post-implementation reflections reinforced the value of hands-on, experiential learning. Scott noted that tools like GTM boosted engagement by letting students “*experiment with real-life scenarios*” (Interview), while Yvette emphasized how Quick, Draw! demystified machine learning through direct interaction with input-output cycles: “*We*

should find more tools like *Quick, Draw!* for students to experience... Letting them further explore the underlying mechanisms” (Interview).

Furthermore, the teachers demonstrated their capacity for proactive problem-solving in adapting AI tools. For example, when students became confused while training the image recognition model on GTM, Scott identified the source of the confusion: non-standardized target objects (i.e., using various types of waste bags, as seen in Figure 1, left). He then decided to standardize the task using specific waste bags from an MSW charging scheme (Figure 1, right) as the training objects, enhancing the task authenticity. Due to the scarcity of these bags at the time, Scott visited multiple convenience stores to procure them and shared this effort with the students during the lesson: “*I ran to several convenience stores for the bags*” (Lesson Observation). As a result, the students better understood the task setting and successfully developed the corresponding AI model.

Figure 1. Non-standard target objects (left) and a standard designated bag as the target object (right).

3.3. The Dual Role of Modular Design in AI Education Adoption

Initially, the teachers exhibited a high degree of dependency on the research team for activity design, preferring that the team provide complete teaching content. Accordingly, the structured guidance of the modules (including step-by-step procedures and visual aids) lowered the implementation threshold. Winnie noted that the resources clarified uncertainties: “*We can identify the problems [within the resources] and instantly ask you if unclear*” (Interview). Scott advocated for the necessity of modularity for scalability: “*It enables teachers to start first, improve through trial and error... critical for primary schools*” (Interview). However, adoption differed among the teachers. Scott, the most experienced teacher, proactively customized the activities based on his previous STEM teaching experience. Meanwhile, the two younger teachers, Winnie and Yvette, preferred following the original design and focused on the integrity of delivering the content. Scott observed: “*The other two teachers are younger, still being trained in our atmosphere to complete tasks. But when I am a bit older, I would think that if some things can be cut and are not that important, I'd rather spend more time on essential aspects*” (Interview). These differences suggest that professional stage can affect AI integration. The experienced teacher demonstrated adaptable innovativeness, while the younger teachers relied on the well-structured content to avoid the risk of uncertainty. This divergence highlights the dual role of modular design—standardizing implementation for broad adoption while enabling adaptable educators to innovate within flexible frameworks.

4. Discussion

4.1. Scaffolding AI Education: Bridging Tools, Dependency and Autonomy

Modular instructional design and low-code AI tools collectively function as dual scaffolding mechanisms, lowering barriers to AI education adoption. While modular resources enable teachers to bypass content-reconstruction challenges and focus on pedagogical execution, low-code tools simplify technical implementation through drag-and-drop interfaces (Kim & Kwon, 2024). However, both approaches risk perpetuating dependency: teachers remain reliant on predefined modules for lesson design and prepackaged tool workflows that obscure algorithmic transparency, exemplifying the limitations of over-scaffolding—where rigid structures inhibit autonomous conceptual exploration.

To foster sustained autonomy, teacher professional development (TPD) for AI education must strategically balance structured support (e.g., modular instructional designs) to reduce entry barriers with adaptive competency-building. This dual approach addresses AI's inherent complexity while empowering educators to innovate beyond prescriptive frameworks. Future research should refine the AI-integrated Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model (Ng et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2021), bridging pre-service training in higher education with in-service TPD to position educators as intentional designers of AI pedagogy.

For technological knowledge (TK) (Koehler & Mishra, 2005), future designs should integrate explanatory scaffolding—layered interfaces that progressively reveal AI principles (e.g., CNN Explainer), enabling learners to transition from basic algorithmic logic to complex applications. Additionally, with GenAI's rapid development, educators and learners can leverage personalized programming assistants to interpret complex concepts and debug code (Boguslawski et al., 2025). Notably, effectively utilizing these tools requires foundational proficiency in GenAI applications. By strengthening TK, educators can demystify AI's 'black box' in classrooms, ensuring sustained technical accessibility.

4.2. PCK-Driven Collaborations among Differentiated Educators for Effective TPD

This study observed divergent trajectories in AI instructional design adoption among three teachers, shaped by their professional development stage. The experienced educator demonstrated agency in innovating module content, suggesting that structured modules can act as catalysts for teacher-led innovation rather than rigid scripts. In contrast, novice teachers adhered closely to pre-set workflows, prioritizing fidelity to mitigate risks associated with unfamiliar AI pedagogies—a behavior consistent with early-career teachers' reliance on external guidance to navigate complexity (Berliner, 2004). Notably, even the most novice teacher contributed ideas for integrating individual innovations to refine the design. As the teachers' pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) surpassed the modules' preset boundaries, this finding echoes Desimone's (2009) assertion that PCK maturation enables educators to adapt standardized resources to context-specific needs. To leverage such dynamics, we propose differentiated collaborative strategies for TPD. First, scaffold early-career teachers through cognitive apprenticeships (Kolikant et al., 2006), pairing them with seasoned peers to co-design modules, thereby reducing anxiety while fostering creative agency. Second, institutionalize cross-phase communities of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991), where veteran teachers model iterative design processes, demystifying innovation for novices.

Nevertheless, this study reveals that modular STEM activities provide primary educators with accessible entry points for AI instruction. However, sustained integration requires structured TPD that extends beyond basic adoption. While teachers demonstrated adaptive reuse of STEM pedagogy in AI contexts, effective curriculum integration necessitates ongoing support to ensure age-appropriate learning. Although initial success largely stems from educators' prior STEM expertise, long-term efficacy depends on TPD aligned with TPACK, fostering autonomous pedagogical innovation rather than passive compliance. Crucially, TPD must also prioritize educators' critical evaluation of AI tools, particularly the epistemic assumptions of these technologies and their alignment with the constructionist principles of STEM education.

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